

2,10-Disubstituted-phenothiazine as Anti-inflammatory Agents

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Phenothiazine derivatives have been reported to possess various biological activities including anti-inflammatory¹. This prompted us to synthesise some new compounds, viz. Δ^2 -triazoline and thiazolidinone derivatives of 2-acetylphenothiazine. These compounds have been screened for anti-inflammatory activity against carrageenin induced oedema in albino rats and showed varying degree of anti-inflammatory activity. The structures of the compounds have been established by ir, ¹H nmr and mass spectral data.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Compounds were checked for their homogeneity by tlc on silica gel G. Infrared spectra were determined on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord 157 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian 90D spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a JMSD-300 instrument with 2000 data. All compounds gave satisfactory results for C, H and N.

2-Acetylphenothiazine² (m.p. 188–89°) (1), 2-acetyl-10-chloroacetylphenothiazine² (m.p. 144–45°) and 2-acetyl-10-hydrazinoacetylphenothiazine³ (m.p. 216°) (2) were prepared by the reported methods.

Preparation of arylidenes (3a-f) : To a solution of compound 2 (0.01 mol) in dry benzene (50 ml) and a few drops of glacial acetic acid, was added the respective benzaldehyde (0.01

mol), and the mixture was refluxed for 12–16 h. The solvent was then distilled off to yield a gummy residue which was washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) and crystallised from appropriate solvent : 3a, m.p. 134° (EtOH), m/z 419 (M⁺; 100%), 418 (M-H; 2), 404 (M-CH₃; 4), 268 (59), 122 (33) and 95 (8), ν_{\max} 1720 (C=O), 3400 (NH), 1620 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ 2.30 (3H, s, ArCOCH₃), 2.45 (2H, s, NCOCH₂), 2.75 (1H, s, NH exchangeable), 6.5–8.2 (11H, m, ArH), 8.45 (1H, s, N=CH); 3b (R = 3-Cl), 127° (DMF-H₂O); 3c (R = 4-Cl), 187° (MeOH); 3d (R = 2,4-Cl₂), 112° (EtOH); 3e (R = 2-CH₃),

145° (C₆H₆), **3f** (R = 2-OCH₃), 116° (benzene-ether); *m/z* 431 (*M*⁺; 100%), 430 (*M*-H; 2), 400 (*M*-OCH₃; 5), 416 (*M*-CH₃; 6) 268 (54), 134 (22), 77 (5).

Preparation of 4a-f : A solution of the hydrazones (**3a-f**; 1 g) in dry THF was treated with excess ethereal diazomethane in cold. The ether was then evaporated off and the resulting mass was washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) and crystallised from appropriate solvent : **4a** m.p. 243° (EtOH-H₂O), *m/z* 461 (*M*⁺; 100%), 460 (*M*-H; 2), 446 (*M*-CH₃; 3), 268 (51), 168 (37), 88 (11), 57 (10), *v*_{max} 3420 (NH), 1520/1 580 (N-N/C-N) and 1420 (N=N) cm⁻¹, δ 2.25 (3H, s, ArCOCH₃), 2.35(2H, s, NCOCH₂), 2.65(1H, br, NH exchangeable), 5.85 (2H, d *J* 9 Hz, CH₂ of triazoline ring), 6.40 (1H, t, *J* 9 Hz, CH of triazoline ring), 6.7–8.5 (11H, m, ArH); **4b** (R = 3-Cl), 195° (MeOH); **4c** (R = 4-Cl), 208° (benzene/EtCOCH₃); **4d** (R = 2,4-Cl₂), 205° (EtOH); **4e** (R = 2-CH₃), 222° (EtOH-H₂O); **4f** (R = 2-OCH₃), 234° (MeOH), *m/z* 473 (*M*⁺, 100%), 472 (*M*-H; 3), 458 (*M*-CH₃, 9), 268 (52), 180 (38), 57 (12), 107 (7), 77 (6).

Preparation of 5a-f : To a solution of the hydrazones (**3a-f**; 0.01 mol) and triethylamine (0.02 mol), was added thiolactic acid (0.02 mol) dropwise with stirring at ambient temperature and the mixture was kept for 3 days at room temperature and refluxed for 6 h. It was then filtered and the filtrate was concentrated and poured into crushed ice. The resulting solid was crystallised from appropriate solvent : **5a**, m.p. 274° (EtOH), *m/z* 507 (*M*⁺, 100%), 506 (*M*-H; 3), 492 (*M*-CH₃; 5), 268 (53), 122 (16), 86 (12), 57 (7), 42 (13), *v*_{max} 1 680 (C=O), 1 740 (C=O, β -thialactam)⁴ and 3 410 cm⁻¹ (NH), δ 2.25 (3H, s, ArCOCH₃), 2.50 (2H, s, NCOCH₂), 2.70 (1H, br, NH exchangeable), 4.85 (3H, d, *J* 9 Hz, CH₃CH of β -thialactam ring), 5.75 (1H, q, *J* 9 Hz, CH₃CH), 6.60 (1H, m, Ar-CH), 7.20–8.75 (11H, m, ArH); **5b** (R = 3-Cl), 288° (dioxane), **5c** (R = 4-Cl), 291° (MeOH); **5d** (R = 2,4-Cl₂), 255° (benzene-pet. ether); **5e** (R = 2,4-CH₃), 244° (MeOH);

5f (R = 2-CH₃), 264° (DMF-H₂O), *m/z* 519 (*M*⁺, 100%), 518 (*M*-H; 2), 504 (*M*-CH₃; 3), 268 (55), 134 (21), 57 (8), 101 (16), 77 (7), 42 (4).

Anti-inflammatory activity : Anti-inflammatory activity of the compounds was conducted by the reported method⁵. All the compounds were screened at a dose of 50 mg/kg p.o. The result showed that all the eighteen compounds exhibited varying degree (2.3–34.2%) of anti-inflammatory activity. Compound **3f** which was substituted with methoxy group at 2-position showed maximum activity (34.2%). Considering its potential anti-inflammatory activity, it was compared with a standard drug (phenylbutazone). However, at a dose of 50 mg/kg p.o., phenylbutazone was more potent (38.3%) as compared to **2f**. When phenyl ring was substituted with chlorine (at position-4), compound **4c** showed less degree (27.9%) of activity than **3f**. However, the cyclisation of the above hydrazones into their corresponding Δ^2 -triazolines, in general, exhibited greater degree of inhibition of oedema except compound **3f** as compared to the respective parent compounds. Moreover, cyclocondensation of hydrazones resulted into their corresponding thiazolidinones having less degree of protection against carrageenin induced oedema.

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